

Deliverable 1.5: Project leaflet

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Basic information

Project title	Strategies to strengthen scientific excellence and innovation capacity for early diagnosis of gastrointestinal cancers
Project acronym	VISION
Call	H2020-WIDESPREAD-2018-2020
Topic	WIDESPREAD-03-2018
Project type	Coordination and Supporting Action (CSA)
Grant Agreement No.	857381
Nature	DEM (Demonstrator)
Dissemination level	PU (Public)

Executive summary

Two printed promotional materials are foreseen to be released within the VISION project. The first one, leaflet presenting the project objectives, activities and scope will be created within the first 3 months. In addition, an educational flyer focussing on gastrointestinal cancer prevention will be created and disseminated in collaboration with Slovak League Against cancer. In addition, a roll-up banner has been produced although it is not foreseen in the budget. It has been funded by BMC SAV.

1 Leaflets

1.1 VISION project leaflet

This leaflet is a tri-fold brochure, available in both English (Fig. 1A) and Slovak (Fig. 1B) language. The content is clear and easily understandable by the target end-users and any audience. The leaflet includes brief information about the project, the project partners, objectives, outcomes and expected impact. Its printable digital version will be circulated in printed form and handed out at conferences, workshops, meetings or other outreach events. Moreover, an electronic version of the leaflet will be also available for download on the project website to allow every project partner to use it for their own dissemination activities.

Figure 1A. The VISION project leaflet (in English)

PARTNERI

PROJEKT V ČÍSLACH

FINANČE
787.465,-€

TRVANIE
1. Október 2019 – 30. September 2022

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VISION

H2020-WIDESPREAD-2018-2020
Spreading Excellence and Widening Participation

<http://vision.sav.sk>

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STRATÉGIE NA POSILNENIE VEDECKEJ EXCELENTNOSTI A NOVÁČKEJ KAPACITY V OBLASTI VÁŠNEJ DIAGNOSTIKY A MODROJ TRÁVIACIEHO TRAKTU

PROJEKT

Slovensko patrí ku krajinám s najvyšším výskytom zhubných nádorov tráviaceho traktu v Európe. Ide predovšetkým o kolorektálny karcinóm a karcinóm pankreasu. Včasná diagnostika je základom pre zvýšenie percenta prežívania pacientov a zlepšenie kvality ich života. Spolupráca s významnými vedeckými inštitúciami prispieje ku zvýšeniu kvality výskumu, prenosu vedeckých výsledkov do klinickej praxe a zlepšeniu úrovne odborného vzdelávania.

STRATÉGIE

- Budovanie medzinárodných spoluprác
- Výmena poznatkov a vedeckých ideí
- Zdieľanie know-how, expertíz a osvedčených postupov
- Využitie moderných technológií

ŠTRUKTÚRA

- Manažment
- Vedecká excelentnosť v oblasti výskumu a liečby nádorov tráviaceho traktu
- Osvojovanie si moderných technológií a nových zručností
- Prekonávanie bariér medzi výskumom a klinickou praxou
- Etické otázky

CIELE

- Vedecká excelentnosť
- Nové možnosti onkologického výskumu
- Profesionálny rozvoj začínajúcich výskumných pracovníkov a lekárov
- Kvalitné vzdelávanie
- Zvýšené povedomie verejnosti o nutnosti prevencie

NÁSTROJE

- Špecializované kurzy
- Akademické pobyty
- Semináre
- Pozvané prednášky
- Letná škola pre študentov
- Konferencie
- Súťaže
- Spolupráca pri vzdelávaní doktorandov
- Aktivity pre laickú verejnosť

VUŽITE VÝSLEDKOV

- Publikácie v renomovaných vedeckých časopisoch
- Spoločné výskumné projekty
- Prezentácie na vedeckých podujatiach
- Dostupnosť moderných technológií
- Prenos poznatkov do klinickej praxe
- Budovanie spoluprác
- Aplikovaný výskum

Figure 1B. The VISION project leaflet (in Slovak)

1.2 VISION educational flyer

The VISION educational flyer focusing on GI cancer prevention will be prepared. A printable digital version of this flyer will be circulated in printed form and handed out at universities, hospitals and any outreach activities co-organized by Cancer Research Foundation (CRF). An electronic version of the flyer will be also available for download on the project website (Slovak public domain).

2 Roll-up banner

A project roll-up banner has been produced in order to give an additional effective aid to the dissemination activities. The project's roll-up contains the very basic information about the project (Fig. 3). The roll-up banner focuses on the visual aspects and its main purpose is to catch the audience attention. The content of the roll-up is clear and easily understandable by the target end users. From the layout and design point of view, the banner shows the VISION project logo, the VISION website heading and the consortium partners' logo. From the content point of view, the roll-up of the VISION project illustrates the main objectives of the VISION project. The banner has already been presented within National Round Table on Science Policy, Together for Improving the Conditions and Quality of Science and Research in Slovakia, organized during Science and Technology Week in Slovakia.

3 Conclusion

The printed promotional materials with the VISION project logo are designed to ensure communication of the project ideas and results as broadly as possible and tailored to the respective target audience groups. Printed materials will be distributed during conferences, workshops and other awareness building events. The dissemination materials (leaflet) will be available in English and Slovak languages.

Figure 3. The VISION roll-up banner